
«I'm not a feminist, but...»

Psychosocial factors underlying support for feminism in Argentina

Joaquín Ungaretti, Edgardo Etchezahar and Talía Gómez Yepes

Previous research suggests that there would be a discrepancy between support for feminism and self-identification with feminist movements, with support being stronger than identification. To understand the reasons behind such inconsistency, scholars have tried different explanations, ranging from a lack of exposure to feminist movements, to personal experiences of gender discrimination, to a simple rejection of the connotation of the word «feminist». However, there are no studies in Argentina that propose a psychosocial-based theoretical model for a more comprehensive understanding of feminism support. The main objective of this study was to test a theoretical model in which conservative values predict right-wing authoritarianism levels, which then influence gender role ideology and gender system justification, and all together predict support for feminism. A total of 1,570 Argentinian adults (female = 55.1%; M_{age} = 38.3 years, SD = 15.6) anonymously participated in the study by completing an online questionnaire. Path analysis revealed that conservative values have a direct effect on the variance of right-wing authoritarianism, which then explains the variance of gender system justification and gender role ideology. Finally, both gender system justification and gender role ideology have a direct effect on the support for feminism. These results show that low support for feminism in Argentina may be motivated by a broad combination of psychosocial variables.

Although the Argentinian feminist movement traces back to the late 19th and early 20th century, the year 2015 implied a turning point in its development due to the surge of the *Ni una menos* movement – meaning no more women killed by gender violence – (Natalucci & Rey, 2018). This movement increased the visibility of women in public life, as well as massive support from people nationally and worldwide (Frain, 2020). The *Ni una menos* movement is so relevant that by 2018 it had been replicated in over 600 cities worldwide (Castro, 2018). Moreover, the movement's social demands have more effectively achieved public policy actions, such as the creation of the Ministry of Women, Gender and Diversity in 2019, the legalization of bill approved in 2020 (Rebon & Gamallo, 2021), and the establishment of a quota for transgender workers in public sector jobs in 2021 (Valente, 2021).

Despite the Argentinian feminist movement's active struggle against the inequalities fostered by traditional gender norms, these conservative patterns still prevail (Friedman & Rodríguez Gustá, 2023; Zaremberg et al., 2021). For example, while women's participation in the paid workforce has increased, the gender gap in housework and childcare has barely narrowed (Faur, 2021). Moreover, the number of femicides and cases of violence against women and girls in Argentina remains dramatic. In 2022 alone, there were 226 direct victims of femicide and 26 victims of related femicide, bringing the total number of victims of gender-based violence to 252 (CSJN, 2022). Current president Javier Milei has abolished the Ministry of Women (Herrán-Ávila, 2023). Moreover, data from the US suggests that while 64% of Americans view feminism as empowering and 42% see it as inclusive, a significant portion of the population holds more critical views. Nearly half (45%) perceive feminism as polarizing, and 30% consider it outdated, highlighting persistent skepticism and division surrounding the term (Barroso, 2020).

Despite the worrying evidence, strong support for feminism has been found to be effective in several areas, including promoting women's physical and mental health (Henderson-King & Zhermer, 2003; Szymanski, 2004), increasing awareness and recognition of sexual harassment (Boyle et al., 2017; Weis et al., 2018), and increasing internal political efficacy (Hegger & Hoffmann, 2021). However, there is a discrepancy between support for feminism and self-identification with feminist movements. In general, support for feminism is stronger (Arnold, 2014) than the identification with feminist movements (Aronson, 2003; Cowan et al., 1992). Furthermore, it has also been shown that women are more supportive of feminism than men, and in both genders, support for feminist ideas is greater than self-identification as a feminist (Burn et al., 2000). Some studies found that younger adults are more likely to identify as feminists and to support feminism compared to older adults (Fitzpatrick Bettencourt et al., 2011). This generational shift is partly attributed to higher levels of education and increased exposure to diverse perspectives (Heger & Hoffmann, 2021). Higher education exposes individuals to diverse viewpoints and critical thinking skills, which tend to foster more progressive attitudes towards gender equality (Glas & Alexander, 2020). Finally, the prevalence of experiences of sexual harassment can play a crucial role in shaping and reinforcing support for feminist ideologies (Shi & Zheng, 2020).

In attempting to understand other reasons for support for feminism, scholars have suggested reasons ranging from a lack of exposure to the feminist movement to personal experiences of gender discrimination to a simple rejection of the connotations of the word «feminist» (e.g., Myaskovsky & Wittig, 1997; Reid & Purcell, 2004). However, no studies have been found in the Argentinean context that propose a psychosocial-based theoretical model for a more comprehensive understanding of feminism support.

1. Gender system justification and gender role ideology

As mentioned above, although gender roles have changed in recent decades, these modifications have been asymmetric. While women have moved more quickly into traditionally male jobs, men have moved more slowly into caring activities and jobs historically reserved for women (Croft et al., 2015). The social meaning and value of these shifts in traditional gender roles are still debated in all areas of public life, so it is vital to understand why people oppose groups that promote change in favour of gender equality.

From a psychological perspective, two widely studied gender constructs are gender system justification (Jost & Kay, 2005) and gender role ideology (Eagly & Sczesny, 2019). Gender system justification arises from the general system justification theory (Jost & Banaji, 1994), which aims to explain why people embrace ideologies and beliefs that legitimize social, political, and economic orders even when these may conflict with their personal and group interests (Jost, 2020). One of the mechanisms underlying this counterintuitive process is «that people will ascribe traits to themselves as well as to other people in such a way that the status or role that they occupy in society is justified» (Jost & Banaji, 1994, p. 13). This process highlights the influence of stereotypes in the perpetuation of social inequalities and emphasizes that they can be used to rationalize or deny the unfairness of systems (Jost, 2019).

All feminist ideologies agree on the fundamental concept that the current situation of inequity between the sexes needs to change to achieve gender equality. Because of this challenging agenda, antifeminist backlash may be caused in part by the desire to defend the social system's credibility. For example, Becker and Wright (2011) demonstrate that gendered system justifications mediate the effects of sexism on women's engagement in collective action. Besides, other studies suggest that when participants' system was threatened or system justification was chronically high, greater disagreement was expressed when statements were attributed to a feminist rather than a non-feminist (Yeung et al., 2014). Jost and Kay (2005) developed the more specific gender system justification theory, with two main aims. First, to understand how and why women may support the current gender role status quo, even when it appears to be in conflict with their interests; and second, to analyze the social and psychological backgrounds and implications of supporting status quo, especially for women as a disadvantaged group (Dirilen-Gumus, 2011). Research showed that the more women identified with their nation, the more they supported the gender system and endorsed ambivalent sexist views (Caricati et al., 2022). Besides, women's (but not men's) support for the gender system increases after the priming with complementary gender stereotypes that see feminine attributes as separate but equal in value to masculine attributes (Jost & Kay, 2005). With regard to the variables that increase men's acceptance of the traditional gender system, it was found that men's support for the status

quo increases when they are exposed to the idea that gender roles are fixed rather than malleable, and when the strength of identification with one's own group is greater (Kray et al., 2017). The results of another study developed during a large feminist rally because of Donald Trump's inauguration in 2017 in the United States indicated that gender system justification decreased over time, but only in low-identified men with high exposure to the rally.

On the contrary, for men highly identified with their gender, gender system justification increased after high exposure to the rally. Finally, no changes were observed in gender system justification for women (Saguy & Szekeres, 2018). Other findings suggest that men and women who considered God as male or were primed with a male image of God scored higher in gender system justification and therefore support the status quo (Howard et al., 2020). More results along these lines indicate that for both men and women, gender system justification was positively associated with different rape myths (Martini & De Piccoli, 2020), with propensity to blame a female rape victim (Stahl et al., 2010), as well as with support for girl child marriage in Turkey (Kaynak et al., 2023).

As mentioned above, gender role ideology is a relevant variable to consider when analyzing attitudes towards gender inequality and feminism related outcomes. Gender roles have been mainly focused on ideas of masculinity associated with strength and determination, and conceptions of femininity associated with kindness and virtuosity (Bem, 1974). From this perspective, gender roles refer to the social roles and behaviors that are identified by certain cultures as appropriate for men and women, including the basic attitudes and emotions that are traditionally considered constitutive of what it means to be a man or a woman (Eagly & Wood, 1991; Spence & Helmreich, 1980). Conventionally, these expectations have portrayed women as more communal – highlighting their concern with others and emotional sensitivity – and men as more agentic – underlining their independence and instrumental competence – (Eagly & Sczesny, 2019; Moya et al., 2006). Although the asymmetries between gender roles have been reduced and gender conceived as a binary construct has been revisited (Eagly et al., 2020; Hyde et al., 2019), these expectations still influence people's daily life. For example, there is evidence that the problem of gender discrimination is more serious in people from developing countries than in developed countries (Glick et al., 2015), and that people in the former adhere more to traditional gender roles. Furthermore, a study developed by Lonsway et al. (2008) found that a weaker support for feminism was associated with greater acceptance of sexual harassment-related myths that deny or trivialize men's harassment of women. In this context, women who passively accept traditional gender roles and stereotypes – and are deeply influenced by patriarchal society – will be more likely to consider some intermediate forms of harassment as innocent pranks or normal social situations that women should tolerate. Some may even go so far as to blame the victim, believing that sexual harassment is caused by scantily dressed women whose intention was to seduce the harasser (Gerger et al., 2007; Herrera

et al., 2014, 2017). Besides, progressist values and empathy were found as mediators variables related to sexual harassment victim blaming and perpetrator blaming (Rollero & Pagliaro, 2022).

2. The implications of values and authoritarianism in gender system justification and gender roles ideology

Even if gender related variables may directly impact on the support for feminism, other broader psychological constructs may also have a part in this process. This is the case of values, which «serve as guiding principles in people's lives, influencing thought and action» (Feather & McKee, 2012, p. 2481). One of Schwartz's (1996) value types is conservation, which encompasses security, conformity, and tradition values reflecting an aim to protect stability. Regarding their relevance for intergroup relationships, there is evidence that conservative values correlate with less support for feminism (Precopio & Ramsey, 2017).

As important drivers of thought and action, values may together influence individuals' ideological attitudes, such as right-wing authoritarianism (RWA, Feather & McKee, 2012). As described by Altemeyer (1988), people with high levels of authoritarianism are extremely self-righteous and defend a high acceptance of traditional norms and values, a high acceptance of authorities perceived as legitimate in the exercise of power, and a general tendency to attack others seen as a threat to the traditional norms and values. In addition, research has revealed that values play a very important function in people with high authoritarianism. For example, studies based on Schwartz's (1992) value theory found that authoritarianism is correlated with value importance ratings (Haddock & Zanna, 1993; Rohan & Zanna, 1996). Therefore, authoritarian people not only maintain traditional values but also rate their values as more important in guiding everyday lives. Higher scores on this attitude are associated with a view of the social world as threatening, an intention to maintain stability in different social spheres, and generalized prejudice (Duckitt & Sibley, 2007). Therefore, it is expected that higher RWA people justify the current gender system and agree with more traditional gender roles (Makwana et al., 2018; Roets et al., 2012; Spaccatini et al., 2019), harming the attitudes towards groups that threaten these societal norms, like feminists (Duckitt, 2006; Duncan et al., 1997; Haddock et al., 1994).

3. The present study

We want to contribute to the knowledge of the variables that play an important role in supporting feminism in a context where this movement is in the spotlight because of its demands for more egalitarian gender rights (Natalucci & Rey, 2018). Therefore, for the current research, we expected to test several hypotheses:

H₁: In line with previous studies that have found that support for feminism is stronger (Arnold, 2014) than the identification with feminist movements (Aronson, 2003; Cowan et al., 1992), we expect to find the same pattern in Argentina.

H₂: Based on Burn et al. (2000), women will support and identify themselves with feminism more than men.

H₃: According with previous studies (Fitzpatrick Bettencourt et al., 2011; Glas & Alexander, 2020; Heger & Hoffmann, 2021; Shi & Zheng, 2020), age will be significantly and negatively related to support for feminism, while educational level and sexual harassment experience will be positively related to support for feminism.

H₄: Based on previous research (Makwana et al., 2018; Roets et al., 2012; Spaccatini et al., 2019), right-wing authoritarianism, gender system justification, gender role ideology, and the three conservative values will be significantly and negatively correlated with support for feminism.

H₅: In line with Duckitt (2006), we suggest that right-wing authoritarianism activated by conservation values may drive the gender system justification and the gender role ideology which could, in turn, negatively influence support for feminism.

4. Method

4.1. Participants

Participants were recruited through social media, controlled by sex, age, and education level according to the national census (INDEC, 2011). The final sample for the study was 1,570 participants, between 18 and 80 years old. The mean age of the entire sample was 38.37 ($SD = 15.65$), 55.1% was female ($n = 865$), 44.1% male ($n = 692$), and 0.8% non-binary ($n = 13$). Also, 8.5% ($n = 133$) finished primary school, 59% ($n = 926$) finished secondary school, 17.2% ($n = 270$) finished tertiary education, and 15.4% ($n = 241$) finished university studies.

The sample size was determined in accordance with the criteria proposed by Lliyasa and Etikan (2021), based on three-quota proportional fixation, taking into account gender, age, and Argentina's geographic regions (Table 1). The sample size was calculated for a 95% CI, with a tolerated margin of error of 5%, based on data from a national survey conducted by INDEC (2020).

4.2. Measures

The data was collected through a self-report questionnaire that included:

Support for feminism. In order to evaluate this construct, participants were asked: «With 1 being *very weak* and 10 being *very strong*, how much do you support feminism?» (Gómez Yepes et al., 2023).

Table 1
Distribution of the sample across the country

Geographic region	<i>f</i>	%
Autonomous City of Buenos Aires	166	10.8
Greater Buenos Aires	457	29.8
Interior Buenos Aires Province	181	11.8
Region 1 (Córdoba, Santa Fe, Mendoza, San Luis, San Juan)	224	14.6
Region 2 (Salta, Jujuy, Catamarca, La Rioja, Santiago del Estero, Tucumán)	142	9.3
Region 3 (Misiones, Chaco, Formosa, Entre Ríos y Corrientes)	181	11.8
Patagonia Region (La Pampa, Río Negro, Neuquén, Chubut, Santa Cruz, Tierra del Fuego)	183	11.9
Total	1,534	100

Gender System Justification (GSJ). We used Jost and Kay's (2005) eight-item scale. Using a scale from 1 = *Strongly disagree* to 6 = *Strongly agree*, participants indicated their agreement with how society currently treats gender in terms of whether the system is fair and whether it should be changed. The GSJ scale include items like «Most policies relating to gender and the sexual division of labor serve the greater good» and «Society is set up so that men and women usually get what they deserve». Higher scores indicate greater levels of gender system justification.

Gender Role Ideology scale (GRI). The reduced local version (Etchezahar, 2020) of the scale composed of 12 items (Moya et al., 2006) was administered, with statements such as «If a child is sick and both parents work, it is best for the mother to be the one to ask for leave at work to take care of him/her», «Extramarital relationships are more condemnable in women than in men», or «Even if a woman works, it should be the man's responsibility to be the economic breadwinner of the family». The scale has a Likert-type response format with five anchors ranging from 1 = *Totally disagree* to 5 = *Totally agree*.

Right-Wing Authoritarianism scale (RWA). An abbreviated version (six items) of the original *Right-Wing Authoritarianism* scale (Altemeyer, 1996) was used, adapted and validated to the Argentinean context (Etchezahar, 2012) with a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = *Strongly disagree* to 5 = *Strongly agree*. Higher scores address higher levels of authoritarianism. The internal consistency and the construct validity results ($.98 < CFI < .99$; $.04 < RMSEA < .07$) were adequate.

Portrait Values (PVQ). We administered the adapted and validated to the Argentina context (Expósito & Marsollier, 2022) conservation dimensions (Tradition, Conformity, and Security) of the *Portrait Values Questionnaire* (PVQ, Schwartz & Rubel-Lifschitz, 2009). The complete scale has 40 items, of which 13 have been used: 5 for Security, 4 for Conformity and 4 for Tradition, corresponding to the conservation dimension. The scale has a five-point Likert-type

scale ranging from 1 = *Strongly disagree* to 5 = *Strongly agree*. Higher scores address higher levels of each value.

Self-identification as feminist. In order to assess this variable, participants were asked: «Being 1 = *Not at all* and 10 = *Completely*, do you consider yourself a feminist?» (Gómez Yepes et al., 2023).

Sexual harassment perception. Participants were asked if «Did you or someone close to you experience any situation of sexual harassment?» (Gómez Yepes et al., 2023), with possible answers being: 1 = *Never* and 5 = *Many times*.

Sociodemographic variables questionnaire. We asked for participants gender (1 = *Male*, 2 = *Female*), age, and educational level (1 = *Complete primary education*, 2 = *Complete secondary education*, 3 = *Complete university education*, 4 = *Postgraduate*).

4.3. Procedure and data analysis

The subjects were invited to participate voluntarily, requesting their informed consent. Furthermore, they were informed that the data derived from this research would be used only for academic and scientific purposes under the Argentinean National Law 25.326 that protects personal data. The Research Ethics Committee, through the CEISH (Evaluation and Monitoring Committee for Research with Human Beings), approved the project (Code CEID2024_09). Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 20.0 (Arbuckle, 2019) and EQS 6.1 (Bentler, 2007) for SEM. Considering the path analysis illustrated in Figure 1, the observed variables were employed to conduct the test. Similarly, the effects of age and gender were controlled (in both cases, the results were not statistically significant).

5. Results

5.1. Support and self-identification with feminism according to age and gender

In order to test H_1 , we asked the participants how much they support feminism, with 1 = *Very weak* and 10 = *Very strong* support, finding a mean score of 5.64 ($SD = 3.26$). The mean decreases when asking to what extent they «Consider themselves as feminist», being 4.28 ($SD = 3.45$) ($t = 12.477$; $p < .001$; Cohen's $d = .31$). However, when analyzing the same questions according to gender in line with H_2 , significant differences were observed. Regarding the support for feminism ($t = 6.131$; $p < .001$; Cohen's $d = .31$), men obtained lower scores ($M = 5.07$; $SD = 3.05$) than women ($M = 6.08$; $SD = 3.36$). As for the self-identification as feminist ($t = 10.779$; $p < .001$; Cohen's $d = .55$), men ($M = 3.25$; $SD = 2.87$) also obtained significant lower scores than women ($M = 5.08$; $SD = 3.66$). Likewise, as stated

Figure 1

Path analysis with variables underlying support for feminism in Argentina

Note. $\chi^2 = 273,490$, $df = 10$; $NFI = .929$; $IFI = .932$; $CFI = .931$; $SRMR = .0603$; $RMSEA = .084$ [.072 – .098].

in H_3 , significant and negative relationships were found between the support for feminism and the age of the participants ($r = -.139$; $p < .001$), as well as significant but positive relations with their educational level ($r = .161$; $p < .001$) (Table 2). Finally, significant and positive relationships were also found between the support for feminism and the perception of having personally experienced (or someone close to them) a sexual harassment episode ($r = .319$; $p < .001$) (Table 2).

5.2. Relationships between the support for feminism and psychosocial variables

Next, as can be seen in Table 2, we analyzed the relationships between the support for feminism and gender system justification, gender role ideology, right-wing authoritarianism, and conservative values (tradition, conformity, security).

As seen in Table 2, and in line with H_4 , all the relationships between the support for feminism and the rest of the variables were significant and negative, although with different strengths. The strongest relationships are those obtained between support for feminism, right-wing authoritarianism, gender system justification, and gender role ideology. Furthermore, the relationships between conservative values and support for feminism are also significant and negative but with less strength, with security being the one that presents the greatest strength of association, followed by conformity and tradition.

Table 2
Relations between the support for feminism and psychosocial variables

	Range	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1. Support for feminism	1-10	5.64	3.26	-	-.549**	-.531**	-.566**	-.355**	-.391**	-.415**	.319**	.841**	-.139**	-.160**	.161**	
2. GSJ	1-5	2.67	.90	.79	.482**	.514**	.341**	.333**	.328**	.377**	-.333**	-.559**	.087**	.209**	.111*	
3. GRI	1-5	1.97	.80	.72	.522**	.332**	.325**	.324**	.324**	.324**	-.286**	-.511**	.159**	.160**	.121*	
4. RWA	1-5	2.88	1.11	.83	.453**	.443**	.499**	.499**	.499**	.499**	-.196**	-.545**	.037	.064*	.131*	
5. Tradition	1-10	3.42	1.12	.79	.498**	.498**	.498**	.498**	.498**	.498**	-.147**	-.350**	.078**	-.006	.024	
6. Conformity	1-10	3.55	1.11	.80	.475**	.475**	.475**	.475**	.475**	.475**	-.204**	-.401**	.129**	.032	.087*	
7. Security	1-10	3.98	.93	.76	-.159**	-.159**	-.159**	-.159**	-.159**	-.159**	-.405**	-.405**	.063*	-.037	.100*	
8. Sexual harassment perception	1-5	2.71	1.07	-.368**	-.278**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	-.270**	.134*
9. Self-identification as feminist	1-10	4.28	3.45	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	-.154**	.091
10. Age	18-80	38.37	15.65	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	-.086**	.141*
11. Gender	1-2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.101*
12. Educational level	1-4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note. Cronbach's α in the diagonal; GSJ = Gender System Justification; GRI = Gender Role Ideology; RWA = Right-Wing Authoritarianism. ** $p < .001$, * $p < .01$.

5.3. Psychosocial factors underlying support for feminism in Argentina

Finally, we conducted a path analysis to test H_5 in which right-wing authoritarianism is activated by conservation values (tradition, conformity, and security), which then drives the gender system justification and the gender role ideology, which, in turn, negatively influences support for feminism (Figure 1).

We supported H_5 since conservation values showed a positive and significant association with each other, while having a direct effect that accounted for 33% of the variance on right-wing authoritarianism. Likewise, as expected, we found a direct and significant effect of right-wing authoritarianism on both gender related constructs, explaining 26% of the variance in gender system justification and 33% of gender role ideology – gender system justification also contributed to the GRI variance. RWA totally mediate the predictors' effects. Finally, both gender system justification and gender role ideology accounted for 39% of the total variance on support for feminism.

6. Discussion

This study aimed to shed light on the psychosocial factors underlying support for feminism in Argentina, in a context of active struggles against the inequalities fostered by traditional gender norms. Using a national sample, we provide evidence that low support for feminism can be motivated by a broad combination of psychosocial variables.

First, according to the poll by the Pew Research Center (2022) developed in the US, we also found medium levels of support for feminism in Argentina. However, self-identification with feminism was even lower. These inconsistencies found in our Country are also coherent with previous studies where support for feminism was generally stronger (Arnold, 2014) than the identification with feminist movements (Aronson, 2003; Cowan et al., 1992). If we disaggregate this information according to what was stated in H_2 and H_3 , we found that women support and identify themselves with feminism more than men and that age is significantly and negatively related to support for feminism. On the contrary, educational level and experience of sexual harassment are significantly positively related to support for feminism. There are several factors that may have contributed to these results in Argentina. One important factor may be that Argentina, like other countries in the world, finds itself within a hybrid reality where social media are integrated into all aspects of economic, social, and political life (Friedman & Rodríguez Gustá, 2023). This scenario provides a platform for anti-feminist voices to spread misinformation and sow discord.

Another factor is the increasingly polarized political landscape, which has made it more difficult for people to find common ground on issues of gender equality. This polarized political scenario about gender equality has had its greatest expression in

the recent dismantling of the Ministry of Women by the current president Javier Milei (Herrán-Ávila, 2023). Despite these challenges, there are also several reasons to be optimistic about the future of feminism. The #MeToo movement has highlighted the pervasiveness of sexual harassment and assault, and it has sparked a global conversation about gender equality. In addition, younger generations are also more likely to identify themselves as feminist than older generations, suggesting that feminism is becoming more mainstream. There is a difference between the support for feminism and the support for specific feminist goals. While some people may have a negative view of feminism as a movement, they may still support individual feminist goals, such as equal pay for equal work or access to reproductive healthcare. Although it is necessary to further explore these findings, significant and positive relationships were also found between support for feminism and the perception of having personally experienced (or having someone close to them experience) sexual harassment. As mentioned previously (Weis et al., 2018), strong support for feminism, as well as a feminist identity, may increase their awareness of sexual harassment.

Regarding H_4 and H_5 , we found that all the psychosocial variables tested here were significantly and negatively correlated with support for feminism. The path analysis conducted in this study provided strong support for Hypothesis 5 (H_5), demonstrating that conservation values are positively and significantly associated with each other and have a direct effect on right-wing authoritarianism (RWA). Specifically, conservation values accounted for 33% of the variance in RWA, indicating that individuals who prioritize these values are more likely to exhibit higher levels of authoritarian attitudes. The path coefficients reveal that the interrelations among conservation values not only reinforce each other but also collectively contribute to the emergence of RWA, highlighting the central role of these values in shaping authoritarian tendencies (Feather & McKee, 2012). Further analysis revealed that RWA, as hypothesized, has a direct and significant impact on both gender-related constructs examined in the study: gender system justification (GSJ) and gender role ideology (GRI). RWA explained 26% of the variance in GSJ and 33% of the variance in GRI, signifying that individuals with higher authoritarian tendencies are more likely to endorse traditional gender roles and justify the existing gender hierarchy. The direct paths from RWA to these constructs underscore its influence as a mediator between broader value systems and specific gender-related beliefs. Moreover, gender system justification was found to contribute to the variance in gender role ideology, suggesting an interconnectedness where the justification of the gender status quo reinforces adherence to traditional gender roles. Finally, the analysis revealed that GSJ and GRI together accounted for 39% of the total variance in support for feminism. This finding suggests that the endorsement of traditional gender roles and the justification of the gender system are significant predictors of attitudes toward feminism, with higher levels of GSJ and GRI being associated with lower support for feminist principles. The high percentage of variance explained by these constructs indicates that gender-related ideologies are key determinants in shaping one's stance on feminist issues.

The Argentinian feminist movement has faced many campaigns against their gender equality claims, in a context with a significant emergence of right-wing political parties, as well as authoritarian, nationalist, and xenophobic forces that aim to «normalize» inequalities (Zaremborg et al., 2021). As in multiple other studies, we also found that authoritarian attitudes are positively related with both traditional gender role ideologies and gender system justification (Makwana et al., 2018; Roets et al., 2012; Spaccatini et al., 2019), having a negative effect on the attitudes towards groups that threaten these societal norms like feminists (Duckitt, 2006; Duncan et al., 1997; Haddock et al., 1994). This may indicate that in Argentina, individuals who score higher on measures of authoritarian attitudes are more likely to hold traditional views about gender roles and believe that the current gender system is fair and just. One possible explanation for this relationship is that traditional gender role ideologies and gender system justification may promote a worldview that is incompatible with the feminist movement in Argentina. While the *Ni una menos* social movement challenges traditional gender roles and advocates for social change (Rebon & Gamallo, 2021), people high in traditional gender role ideologies and gender system justifications seek to reinforce traditional norms and values and maintain the status quo.

The present study is of interest from a theoretical perspective, as it offers insights into the ways in which psychosocial factors in Argentina shape attitudes towards feminism. It also can contribute to the global feminist discourse by providing insights into how feminism is perceived and supported in different cultural contexts. Besides, these findings provide a basis for comparative studies with other countries or regions, contributing to a broader theoretical framework for understanding global feminist movements and their varying levels of support.

On the other hand, this study also offers some practical implications, since understanding the level of support for feminism can inform policymakers about public attitudes toward gender equality. This can guide the development and implementation of policies aimed at promoting gender equity, such as educational programs, workplace regulations, and anti-discrimination laws. Moreover, insights from the study can be used to design targeted educational and awareness programs that address misconceptions about feminism and promote gender equality. Educational institutions can integrate these findings into curricula to foster a more inclusive and egalitarian society.

6.1. Limitations and future directions

Overall, this study offers some insights for future work. As an example, future work could explore the mediation of other psychosocial variables on the effects that values, right-wing authoritarianism, gender system justification, and gender role ideologies have on the support for feminism (e.g., social dominance orientation, general

system justification, among others). Besides, attitudes toward feminism scale can be used for a better control of the outcome of this study. Finally, analyzing changes in support for feminism over time can offer theoretical insights into how social movements evolve, gain traction, and impact societal values and norms.

However, our study was not without limitations. For example, the sample size and demographic composition of the participants may not be representative of the wider population, which may affect the generalisability of the findings. Also, the use of self-reported measures of conservative values, authoritarian attitudes, gender system justification, and gender role ideology may introduce bias or inaccuracy due to social desirability and response bias. The study focuses on some specific measures, but others may yield different results. Finally, it is important to note that our study was conducted in a specific cultural context and it is unclear whether the findings can be generalized to other cultures with different gender norms and social structures.

Declarations

The authors did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work. The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The datasets generated by the survey research during the current study are available upon request. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of The Valencian International University Committee for Responsible Conduct in Research and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. In addition, informed consent was obtained from all participants included in the study.

References

- Arbuckle, J. L. (2019). *IBM SPSS Amos 26 User's Guide*. IBM Corporation. https://www.ibm.com/docs/SSLVMB_26.0.0/pdf/amos/IBM_SPSS_Amos_User_Guide.pdf
- Altemeyer, B. (1988). *Enemies of freedom*. University of Manitoba Press.
- Altemeyer, B. (1996). *The authoritarian specter*. Harvard University Press.
- Arnold, A. S. (2014). *Essentialism matters: Silence, fear and the feminist dilemma*. The University of North Carolina at Greensboro.
- Aronson, P. (2003). Feminists or «postfeminists»? Young women's attitudes toward feminism and gender relations. *Gender & Society*, 17(6), 903–922. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243203257145>
- Barroso, A. (2020, July 7). 61% of US women say «feminist» describes them well; many see feminism as empowering, polarizing. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2020/07/07/61-of-u-s-women-say-feminist-describes-them-well-many-see-feminism-as-empowering-polarizing/>

- Becker, J. C., & Wright, S. C. (2011). Yet another dark side of chivalry: Benevolent sexism undermines and hostile sexism motivates collective action for social change. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 101(1), 62–77. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0022615>
- Bem, S. (1974). The measurement of psychological androgyny. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 42, 165–174.
- Bentler, P. (2007). On tests and indices for evaluating structural models. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 42, 825–829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2006.09.024>
- Boyle, K., Barr, A., & Clay-Warner, J. (2017). The effects of feminist mobilization and women's status on Universities' reporting of rape. *Journal of School Violence*, 16(3), 317–330. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2017.1318580>
- Burn, S. M., Aboud, R., & Moyles, C. (2000). The relationship between gender social identity and support for feminism. *Sex Roles*, 42, 1081–1089. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1023/A:1007044802798>
- Caricati, L., Ferrari, A., & Kevin Owuamalam, C. (2022). Strongly identifying Italian women support their gender system because they accept their Italian way of doing things. *Psicologia sociale – Social Psychology Theory & Research*, 17(3), 427–439. <https://doi.org/10.1482/105496>
- Castro, L. (2018). La acción colectiva feminista, ¿de la lucha de clases a la lucha de géneros? Apuntes para la comprensión/práctica de los movimientos sociales, en torno al caso «Ni Una Menos». *Ciencia Política*, 13, 19–61.
- Cowan, G., Mestlin, M., & Masek, J. (1992). Predictors of feminist self-labeling. *Sex Roles*, 27, 321–330. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00289942>
- Croft, A., Schmader, T., & Block, K. (2015). An underexamined inequality: Cultural and psychological barriers to men's engagement with communal roles. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 19(4), 343–370. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868314564789>
- CSJN, Oficina de la Mujer (2022). *Registro Nacional de Femicidios de la Justicia Argentina*. <https://om.csjn.gob.ar/consultaTalleresWeb/public/documento=170>
- Dirilen-Gumus, O. (2011). Differences in system justification with respect to gender, political conservatism, socio-economic status and religious fundamentalism. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 2607–2611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.510>
- Duckitt, J. (2006). Differential effects of right wing authoritarianism and social dominance orientation on outgroup attitudes and their mediation by threat from and competitiveness to outgroups. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 32, 684–696. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/0146167205284282>
- Duckitt, J., & Sibley, C. (2007). Right wing authoritarianism, social dominance orientation and the dimensions of generalized prejudice. *European Journal of Personality*, 21, 113–130. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1002/per.614>
- Duncan, L. E., Peterson, B. E., & Winter, D. G. (1997). Authoritarianism and gender roles: Toward a psychological analysis of hegemonic relationships. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 23(1), 41–49.
- Eagly, A. H., Nater, C., Miller, D. I., Kaufmann, M., & Sczesny, S. (2020). Gender stereotypes have changed: A cross-temporal meta-analysis of US public opinion polls from 1946 to 2018. *American Psychologist*, 75(3), 301–315. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000494>
- Eagly, A. H., & Sczesny, S. (2019). Editorial: Gender roles in the future? Theoretical foundations and future research directions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167297231005>

- Eagly, A. H., & Wood, W. (1991). Explaining sex differences in social behavior: A meta-analytic perspective. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 17(3), 306–315. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/0146167291173011>
- Etchezahar, E. (2012). Las dimensiones del autoritarismo: análisis de la escala de autoritarismo del ala de derechas (RWA). *Revista de Psicología Política*, 3, 123–139.
- Etchezahar, E. (2020). La ideología del rol de género según la aceptación de los derechos de la mujer. el matrimonio homosexual y el género. In E. Costa & E. Etchezahar (Eds.) *Diversidad, Identidad, Derechos* (pp. 9–25). Ediciones de la UNLZ.
- Expósito, C., & Marsollier, R. (2022). Los valores y la formación docente. Un análisis axiológico desde el Portrait Values Questionnaire (PVQ-40). *Praxis educativa*, 26(3), 1–21. <https://dx.doi.org/10.19137/praxiseducativa-2022-260310>
- Faur, E. (2021). Inequalities in childcare strategies among domestic workers and teachers in Argentina. *ICDD Working Papers*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.17170/kobra-202101182979>
- Feather, N. T., & McKee, I. R. (2012). Values, right-wing authoritarianism, social dominance orientation, and ambivalent attitudes toward women. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42(10), 2479–2504. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2012.00950.x>
- Fitzpatrick Bettencourt, K. E., Vacha-Haase, T., & Byrne, Z. S. (2011). Older and younger adults' attitudes toward feminism: The influence of religiosity, political orientation, gender, education, and family. *Sex Roles*, 64, 863–874. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/s11199-011-9946-z>
- Frain, K. (2020). How a tweet brought people to the street: Social media and the success of Ni Una Menos. *Undergraduate Journal of Global Citizenship*, 3(2), Article 4. <https://digitalcommons.fairfield.edu/jogc/vol3/iss2/4>
- Friedman, E.J., & Rodríguez Gustá, A.L. (2023). «Welcome to the revolution»: Promoting generational renewal in Argentina's Ni Una Menos. *Qualitative Sociology*, 46, 245–277. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-023-09530-0>
- Gerger, H., Kley, H., Bohner, G., & Siebler, F. (2007). The acceptance of modern myths about sexual aggression scale: Development and validation in German and English. *Aggressive Behavior: Official Journal of the International Society for Research on Aggression*, 33(5), 422–440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.20195>
- Glas, S., & Alexander, A. (2020). Explaining support for muslim feminism in the Arab Middle East and North Africa. *Gender & Society*, 34(3), 437–466. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243220915494>
- Glick, P., Wilkerson, M., & Cuffe, M. (2015). Masculine identity, ambivalent sexism, and attitudes toward gender subtypes: Favoring masculine men and feminine women. *Social Psychology*, 46(4), 210–217. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-9335/a000228>
- Gómez Yepes, T., Etchezahar, E., Sánchez, L., & Mateu, D. N. (2023). Prejuicio sexista y percepción de sociedad machista en estudiantes de Escuela Secundaria. In D. Cobos-Sanchiz, E. López-Meneses, A. Jaén-Martínez, A. H. Martín-Padilla, & Molina-García, L. (Eds.), *Educación y Sociedad: Pensamiento e innovación para la transformación social* (pp. 1947–1951). Dykinson.
- Haddock, G., & Zanna, M. P. (1993). Predicting prejudicial attitudes: The importance of affect, cognition, and the feeling-belief dimension. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Haddock, G., & Zanna, M. P. (1994). Preferring «housewives» to «feminists». *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 18(1), 25–52. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/j.1471-6402.1994.tb00295.x>

- Heger, K., & Hoffmann, C. P. (2021). Feminism! What is it good for? The role of feminism and political self-efficacy in women's online political participation. *Social Science Computer Review*, 39(2), 226–244. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894439319865909>
- Henderson-King, D., & Zhermer, N. (2003). Feminist consciousness among Russians and Americans. *Sex Roles*, 48, 143–155. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022403322131>
- Herrán-Ávila, L. (2023). The reinvention of the Latin American right: Across the hemisphere and beyond, right-wing forces are leveraging the power of internationalism to galvanize hardline «resistance» against a new wave of leftist governments. *NA-CLA Report on the Americas*, 55(1), 25–31.
- Herrera, M. C., Herrera, A., & Expósito, F. (2014). Stop Harassment! Men's reactions to victims' confrontation. *The European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, 6(2), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpal.2014.06.006>
- Herrera, M. C., Herrera, A., & Expósito, F. (2017). To confront versus not to confront: Women's perception of sexual harassment. *European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, 10(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpal.2017.04.002>
- Howard, S., Oswald, D., & Kirkman, M. (2020). The relationship between God's gender, gender system justification and sexism. *The International Journal for the Psychology of Religion*, 30(3), 216–230. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10508619.2020.1737420>
- Hyde, J. S., Bigler, R. S., Joel, D., Tate, C. C., & van Anders, S. M. (2019). The future of sex and gender in psychology: Five challenges to the gender binary. *American Psychologist*, 74(2), 171–193. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000307>
- INDEC (2011). *Censo Nacional de Población, Hogares y Viviendas 2010. Total país y provincias: Resultados definitivos*. Variables seleccionadas, Serie B n. 1. Buenos Aires, Argentina: Autor.
- INDEC (2020). *Incidencia de la pobreza y la indigencia en 31 aglomerados urbanos*. https://www.indec.gob.ar/uploads/informesdeprensa/eph_pobreza_01_19422F5FC20A.pdf
- Jost, J. T., & Banaji, M. R. (1994). The role of stereotyping in system-justification and the production of false consciousness. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 33, 1–27. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/j.2044-8309.1994.tb01008.x>
- Jost, J. T., & Kay, A. C. (2005). Exposure to benevolent sexism and complementary gender stereotypes: Consequences for specific and diffuse forms of system justification. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 88(3), 498–509. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-3514.88.3.498>
- Jost, J. T. (2019). A quarter century of system justification theory: Questions, answers, criticisms, and societal applications. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 58(2), 263–314. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/bjso.12297>
- Jost, J. T. (2020). *A theory of system justification*. Harvard University Press. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.2307/j.ctv13qfw6w>
- Kaynak, B. D., Kaynak Malatyali, M., & Hasta, D. (2023). Hostile sexism and gender system justification predict greater support for girl child marriage in Turkey. *Sex Roles*, 88, 201–209. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/s11199-023-01348-y>
- Kray, L. J., Howland, L., Russell, A. G., & Jackman, L. M. (2017). The effects of implicit gender Role theories on gender system justification: Fixed beliefs Strengthen masculinity to preserve the status quo. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 112(1), 98–115. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/pspp0000124>
- Liyasu, R., & Etikan, I. (2021). Comparison of quota sampling and stratified random sampling. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 10(1), 24–27. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/bbij.2021.10.00326>

- Lonsway, K. A., Cortina, L. M., & Magley, V. J. (2008). Sexual harassment mythology: Definition, conceptualization, and measurement. *Sex Roles, 58*, 599–615.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/s11199-007-9367-1>
- Makwana, A. P., Dhont, K., De keersmaecker, J., Akhlaghi-Ghaffarokh, P., Masure, M., & Roets, A. (2018). The motivated cognitive basis of transphobia: The roles of right-wing ideologies and gender role beliefs. *Sex Roles, 79*, 206–217.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/s11199-017-0860-x>
- Martini, M., & De Piccoli, N. (2020). Predicting bystander intention to intervene: The role of gender-specific system justification and rape myth acceptance for men and women. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*, Article 326.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00326>
- Moya, M., Expósito, F., & Padilla, J. L. (2006). Revisión de las propiedades psicométricas de las versiones larga y reducida de la Escala sobre Ideología de Género. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology, 6*(3), 709–727.
- Myaskovsky, L., & Wittig, M. A. (1997). Predictors of feminist social identity among college women. *Sex Roles, 37*, 861–883. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/BF02936344>
- Natalucci, A. L., & Rey, J. (2018). ¿Una nueva oleada feminista? Agendas de género, repertorios de acción y colectivos de mujeres (Argentina, 2015-2018). *Revista de Estudios Políticos y Estratégicos, 6*(2), 14–34.
- Precopio, R. F., & Ramsey, L. R. (2017). Dude looks like a feminist!: Moral concerns and feminism among men. *Psychology of Men & Masculinity, 18*(1), 78.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/men0000042>
- Rebon, J., & Gamallo, L. A. (2021). Las bases sociales de la protesta en torno al aborto en la Argentina reciente. *Sociedad y religión, 31*(56), 65–65.
- Reid, A., & Purcell, N. (2004). Pathways to feminist identification. *Sex Roles, 50*, 759–769.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1023/B:SERS.0000029095.40767.3c>
- Roets, A., Van Hiel, A., & Dhont, K. (2012). Is sexism a gender issue? A motivated social cognition perspective on men's and women's sexist attitudes toward own and other gender. *European Journal of Personality, 26*(3), 350–359.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1002/per.843>
- Rohan, M. J., & Zanna, M. P. (1996). Value transmission in families. In C. Seligman, J. M. Olson & M. P. Zanna (Eds.), *The psychology of values: The Ontario Symposium* (Vol. 8, pp. 253–276). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Rollero, C., & Pagliaro, S. (2022). Moral foundations and victim blaming in case of non-consensual dissemination of one's sexual images: A preliminary study. *Psicologia sociale, 17*(2), 195–205. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1482/104809>
- Saguy, T., & Szekeres, H. (2018). Changing minds via collective action: Exposure to the 2017 Women's March predicts decrease in (some) men's gender system justification over time. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations, 21*(5), 678–689.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/1368430217750475>
- Schwartz, S. H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. In M. P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 25, pp. 1–65). Academic Press.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60281-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60281-6)
- Schwartz, S. H. (1996). Value priorities and behaviour: Applying a theory of integrated value systems. In C. Seligman, J. M. Olson & M. P. Zanna (Eds.), *The psychology of values: The Ontario Symposium* (vol. 8, pp. 1–24). Lawrence Erlbaum.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203773857>
- Schwartz, S. H., & Rubel-Lifschitz, T. (2009). Cross-national variation in the size of sex differences in values: Effects of gender equality. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 97*(1), 171–185. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015546>

- Shi, X., & Zheng, Y. (2020). Perception and tolerance of sexual harassment: An examination of feminist identity, sexism, and gender roles in a sample of Chinese working women. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 44(2), 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361684320903683>
- Spaccatini, F., Pacilli, M. G., Giovannelli, I., Roccato, M., & Penone, G. (2019). Sexualized victims of stranger harassment and victim blaming: The moderating role of right-wing authoritarianism. *Sexuality and Culture*, 23(3), 811–825. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1007/s12119-019-09592-9>
- Spence, J. T., & Helmreich, R. L. (1980). Masculine instrumentality and feminine expressiveness: Their relationships with sex role attitudes and behaviors. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 5(2), 147–163. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/j.1471-6402.1980.tb00951.x>
- Stahl, G. K., Mäkelä, K., Zander, L., & Maznevski, M. L. (2010). A look at the bright side of multicultural team diversity. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 26(4), 439–447. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scaman.2010.09.009>
- Szymanski, D. M. (2004). Relations among dimensions of feminism and internalized heterosexism in lesbians and bisexual women. *Sex Roles*, 51, 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:SERS.0000037759.33014.55>
- Valente, M. (2021, June 25). Transgender job quota law seen «changing lives» in Argentina. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/article/argentina-lgbt-lawmaking/transgender-job-quota-law-seen-changing-lives-in-argentina-idUSL5N2O72DH>
- Weis, A. S., Redford, L., Zucker, A. N., & Ratliff, K. A. (2018). Feminist identity, attitudes toward feminist prototypes, and willingness to intervene in everyday sexist events. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 42(3), 279–290. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/0361684318764694>
- Yeung, A. W. Y., Kay, A. C., & Peach, J. M. (2014). Anti-feminist backlash: The role of system justification in the rejection of feminism. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 17(4), 474–484. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1177/1368430213514121>
- Zarembeg, G., Tabbush, C., & Friedman, E. J. (2021). Feminism(s) and anti-gender backlash: Lessons from Latin America. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 23(4), 527–534. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2021.1956093>

«I'm not a feminist, but...» Psychosocial factors underlying support for feminism in Argentina

Previous research suggests that there would be a discrepancy between support for feminism and self-identification with feminist movements, with support being stronger than identification. To understand the reasons behind such inconsistency, scholars have tried different explanations, ranging from a lack of exposure to feminist movements, to personal experiences of gender discrimination, to a simple rejection of the connotation of the word «feminist». However, there are no studies in Argentina that propose a psychosocial-based theoretical model for a more comprehensive understanding of feminism support. The main objective of this study was to test a theoretical model in which conservatism values predict right-wing authoritarianism levels, which then influence gender role ideology and gender system justification, and all together predict support for feminism. A total of 1,570 Argentinian adults (female = 55.1%; $M_{age} = 38.3$ years, $SD = 15.6$) anonymously participated in the study by completing an online questionnaire. Path analysis revealed that conservative values have a direct effect on the variance of right-wing authoritarianism, which then explains the variance of gender system justification and gender role ideology. Finally, both

gender system justification and gender role ideology have a direct effect on the support for feminism. These results show that low support for feminism in Argentina may be motivated by a broad combination of psychosocial variables.

Keywords: feminism, gender system justification, gender role, values, right-wing authoritarianism.

Corresponding author: Joaquín Ungaretti, Faculty of Education, Valencian International University, C. del Pintor Sorolla, 21, Ciutat Vella, 46002 Valencia
joaquinjesus.ungaretti@professor.universidadviu.com
ORCID 0000-0003-1185-9139

Edgardo Etchezahar, Autonomous, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Madrid, C/Francisco Tomás y Valiente 3, 28049 Madrid
edgardo.etcchezahar@uam.es
ORCID 0000-0002-3289-194X

Talía Gómez Yepes, Autonomous, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University of Madrid, C/Francisco Tomás y Valiente 3, 28049 Madrid
talia.gomez@uam.es
ORCID 0000-0001-6555-1186